

Strategic Stakeholder Engagement Clarity and Performance of County Government of Kisii, Kenya

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to determine the strategic stakeholder engagement clarity and performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya. The study was guided by goal setting theory, contingency theory and modern organizational theory. The study utilized cross sectional research design and the target population for the study comprised of all middle level management in County. The study employed census since the target population was small. The study utilized primary data sources which was collected by use of structure questionnaires. The questionnaires for the research were structured based on the research objectives. Data analysis techniques used by the study was descriptive statistics and inferential statistics which was computed through multiple regression and correlation analysis. The data collection tool used by the researcher was Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. Analyzed data was presented in frequency distribution tables so as to make it easy for research results description and explanation. Based on the findings, the study concluded that strategic stakeholder engagement clarity has a significant effect on performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya. The study came up with the following recommendations; The county government should have procedural charts for all major stakeholder engagement and orient them on new processes before rolling out. The strategic decisions made by the organization should be communicated to all stakeholders.

Keywords: strategic stakeholder engagement clarity, employed census, employed census, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

1. INTRODUCTION

Managing organizational performance is directly related to organizational sustainability (Park & Choi, 2020). Managing performance in public organizations, however, has been quite challenging due to the complex nature of organizational goals. The goals of public organizations are inclined to be more ambiguous, dynamic, and sometimes multifaceted than those in private organizations (Younis, et al., 2023). Organizational performances are a set of overall preferred results that it wants to accomplish and measure for different levels of hierarchy and can be assessed for individuals, groups, and the entire organization as a whole (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021). Chenhall and Langfield-Smith (2018), argued that an organization cannot sufficiently obtain a competitive advantage unless it connects all strategies to functional processes and information systems. This is because strategic implementation requires individuals at various levels to support the organization's purposes and goals with the same level of commitment (Kathuria et al., 2017). In the energy sector, the Ukrain-Russia conflict and uncertainty in Middle East unleashed a "storm" of unprecedented challenges and uncertainties in the sector worldwide (Gollakota and Shu, 2023, Amamou and Bargaoui, 2022, Lu and Khan, 2023).

Global business environment changes occasioned by increased competition due to deregulations, globalization and technological change have led to an increase in environmental turbulence, thus necessitating continuous change within the organization (Morrison, Ghose, Dam, Hinge, & Hoesch-Klohe, 2017). Given the increasing challenges in the competitive environment, it is evident that successful firms not only have to perform better than their competitors, but they also have to constantly adapt to changing conditions (Henderson & Venkatraman, 2017). These changes have been widely felt across many sectors of industry and commerce. There is a broadly accepted view that the success or failure of a firm is ultimately determined by the competitiveness of its supply chain structure (SCS) (Chopra & Meindl, 2017).

Organizational performances are a set of overall preferred results that it wants to accomplish and measure for different levels of hierarchy and can be assessed for individuals, groups, and the entire organization as a whole (Knies et al., 2016). Thus, performance is success that doesn't exist by itself, but it is a function of individual efforts and the result of action (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021). Change dynamism in modern business environment complicated the management system and challenging effectiveness in performance. Hence, to sustain performance improvement, organization of all structure and size search for strategic fit that allow all parts of the system to be closely integrated and aligned toward actively achieving the desired results. Thus, integration of business resources and activities with organizational strategic priority is termed as strategic alignment as it was used in this study. Strategic alignment is critical trend among contemporary strategic concepts helping organizations to cope up with challenges and altering old work system to productive one (Sharma & Behl, 2023). It is a long-term function that secures organizational survival and protect the continuity of performance improvement (Sha et al., 2020). Strategic implementation alignment allow harmony relation and transparent communication between lower and higher level administrators and staff. This enables organizations to work together and achieve a unified goal through effective communications. It is a source of compatibility and harmony at the organization's internal level due to unified efforts (Abanumay & Mezghani, 2023; Ahmad & Adnan, 2017; Chtourou Ben Amar & Ben Romdhane, 2020).

The basic foundation of strategic implementation alignment is contingency theory that states the fit between certain contextual and organizational factors leads to higher performance (Hanisch & Wald, 2012). There is also configurational theory which suggests strategic alignment as the fit between a firm's strategy and its internal and external factors leads to superior firm performance (Herd et al., 2023). Strategic alignment has different dimensions representing organizational strategic fit with various contextual components (Younis et al., 2023). It includes harmony of business strategy, information technology strategy, organizational infrastructure and processes, and IT infrastructure and processes by (Luftman et al. 2023). Moreover, it encompasses organizational strategic fit with strategies in other functional areas, such as procurement strategy (Knudsen, 2003), human resource management strategy (Shih et al., 2005) and advertising strategy (Boudreau & Watson, 2006). But, the focus of this study was investigation of strategic clarity dimensions like goal clarity, communication, vision clarity and stakeholder engagement clarity effects on organizational performance.

Clarity in strategic statement provides valuable guidance to workers through specific identification of the performance dimensions that organization seeks to optimize (Smith & Thomas, 2020). It shapes workers' attention in the most effective way which in turn, results in the highest performance. Goal, communication, vision and stakeholders involvement clarities are the strategic clarity statements used for this study and represents the degree to which employees understand why the task assigned is relevant or essential (Anderson & Stritch, 2016). It motivates employees to know their contributions are valued for achievements and task performance (Bellamkonda et al., 2021).

Many scholars have attempted to explore implementation and theoretical implication of constructs at practical level given the importance of strategic alignment for the success of organizations performance. However, no common sense were reached about unified constructs and best dimension of strategic alignments (Herd et al., 2018; Reese, 2020; Wamba-Taguimdje et al., 2020). Moreover, the focus of many researchers in the area of strategic alignment is fit between organizational strategic priorities with information technology and/or with external environment. Therefore, the focus of current study was investigation of how clarity in organizational strategic objectives is communicated among the parts in organization and how it affects targeted performance. Though concepts of strategic alignment have been studied and insights into understanding of different dimension of strategic alignment and its impact on organizational performance were established (Al-Surmi, 2016; Ghonim et al., 2022; Sharma & Behl, 2023); those researches mainly focused on three issues as fit between information technology and business strategy, fit between business strategy and competitive environment and as fit between business and marketing strategy. But, alignments between important strategy components as goal, communication and stakeholder engagement clarity through which assigned tasks performed was not yet investigated.

Moreover, prior researchers have generalized strategic alignment as equally applicable concepts to all organization irrespective to size and nature without taking into account the specific strategies of firms and alignment dimensions. Therefore, this study focused on effects of strategic clarity as goal, communication, vision and stakeholder engagement in the performance of county government of Kisii.

In Kenya, approximately 20 percent of nation's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is produced by state corporations. Despite these agencies' contributions to the GDP, the public investment committee notes that only corporations managed to receive a perfect score out of the 130 reports assessed by the Auditor General (ROK, 2017). The main narrative is one of loss, theft, fraud, and flagrant mismanagement, all of which are impeding continuous performance improvement and service delivery. The ineffective use of public funds results from problems with the entire tendering process, including the identification of needs, the creation of bid documents, a lack of competition and transparency, particularly during the bidding process, the evaluation of bids, the awarding of contracts, and inadequate contract supervision. Strategic clarity is critical trend among contemporary strategic concepts helping organizations to cope up with challenges and altering old work system to productive one (Sharma & Behl, 2023). It is a long-term function that secures organizational survival and protect the continuity of performance improvement (Sha et al., 2020).

The performance of county governments in Kenya has been a subject of extensive discussion and analysis, particularly in light of the devolved system of governance established by the 2010 Constitution. The performance of county governments in Kenya is multifaceted, with successes and challenges largely shaped by governance practices, resource allocation, and the political environment. There has been complaints of lack of clarity in goals, roles expectations and vision to enable reduction of costs and wastages in resources (Elia et al. (2023). Counties realm are experiencing financial strain due to high volatility of dollar in the global market. County governments therefore need to pursue sustainable development goals (Markman et al., 2016), engage in sustainability standard adoption (substantive compliance) (Wijen, 2014), as well as target safety-related goals (Gaba and Greve, 2019) and waste-reduction goals (Berchicci and Tarakci, 2022)

Efforts towards enhancing accountability, transparency, citizen participation, and capacity building are essential for achieving the goals of devolution and improving service delivery across the counties (Dong, 2021). In the wake of ever-changing administration, strategic clarity is paramount. Strategic goals and objective clarity significantly helps organizations use their resources effectively to support their business strategies, thus enabling them to increase competitiveness, revenue growth, and profitability (Henderson & Venkatraman, 2017). Continued research and assessment of county performance will further inform policymakers, stakeholders, and citizens in fostering effective governance in Kenya.

Strategic goals and objective clarity is essential for organizations seeking to navigate complex environments and thrive over the long term (Pinelli et al., 2023). By fostering alignment, improving decision-making, enhancing communication, and creating a sense of purpose among employees, organizations can better position themselves to achieve their goals and sustain competitive advantage (Berchicci and Tarakci, 2022). As the landscape continues to evolve, maintaining strategic clarity will be crucial for adaptability and resilience (Smulowitz et al., 2020). Various studies have been done on strategic clarity but majority have focused on other sectors and not counties. For instance, Koskei (2017) investigated strategic alignment and information technology on performance of east Africa Portland cement Kenya. It is evident that studies reviewing the linkage between strategic objective clarity and performance assume that such alignment affects the behavior of individuals within the organization which promotes the achievement of organizational goals (Kim, Kim and Kwon 2020). However, there is a lack of empirical studies on strategic clarity in county government context. Therefore, the study sought to examine the effect of strategic stakeholder engagement clarity on performance of county government of Kisii Kenya.

2. STRATEGIC STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT CLARITY AND PERFORMANCE

Strategic Stakeholder Clarity refers to the clear identification, understanding, and communication of an organization's key stakeholders, their interests, influence, and expectations in relation to strategic goals (Kimani, B 2024). It involves having a well-defined approach to recognizing who the stakeholders are, what they need or expect, and how their roles impact the organization's objectives. This clarity ensures effective stakeholder engagement, alignment of interests, and informed decision-making, ultimately enhancing organizational performance and strategic outcomes. Stakeholder management is crucial for the Ministry of Interior and National Administration to identify and respond to the needs and demands of different groups that are impacted by the ministry's policies and services. Such engagements can be in the form of public

consultations, focus group discussions, and community outreach programs. Stakeholder engagement enables the ministry to increase the effectiveness of its services, foster trust, and make more informed decisions (Coleman, Manyindo, Parker & Schultz 2019).

A study by Uddin, Ong & Matous (2023) showed that ministries with stakeholder engagements included in their strategic communication clarity plans were 40% more likely to meet their service delivery goals. It also emphasized the need to develop different engagement approaches for different stakeholders and the use of technology to increase the number of stakeholders involved.

Effect of stakeholder engagements on the quality-of-service delivery to the public Ferreira (2020) In his article 'Stakeholders' engagement on nature-based solutions,' discusses the effects that stakeholders have had on service delivery to the citizens of Canada. Several stakeholders in Canada including CSIS, frequently collaborate with non-government financial and social businesses, involving those in the private industry, legal community, educational institutions, and manufacturing organizations, to successfully tackle contemporary national security threats as well as other public service delivery impacting Canadians in a way that meets openness and responsibility standards and instills confidence in our efforts. According to the author, the stakeholder engagement strategy strives to ensure that Canadians accept CSIS as a knowledgeable and trustworthy collaborator in safeguarding Canada's social structure and financial stability. He concludes that to establish and maintain lasting connections with major stakeholders, this program publicly collaborates with Canadians in various areas of our civil society and finances to gain insight from other people's perspectives and contribute to developing a common awareness of Canada's national security interests and priorities in public service delivery.

According to Heckert (2020) in his article 'Research Involvement and engagement', stakeholders in the United Kingdom function as key advisors to major companies and other institutions, which in turn improves the quality of services offered to the people. Companies engage their stakeholders in discussion to determine what social and environmental concerns are most important to them regarding company performance, to enhance decision-making and accountability. The Global Reporting Initiative, a globally recognized sustainable development reporting methodology, requires stakeholder engagement. According to the author, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) demands stakeholder input for newly developed guidelines. One fundamental principle of stakeholder engagement is that stakeholders can impact decision-making processes which will improve service delivery. He suggests that firms could increase their stakeholder involvement by actively listening, building respectful relationships, and responding to their issues in a manner that benefits everyone involved.

According to Mziba (2020) in his article 'The role of public participation in service delivery', stakeholders in South Africa play a significant role in project monitoring, financial input, and evaluation to improve service delivery to its citizens. Project monitoring and assessment entail measuring, recording, analyzing, and responding to variances in the project's achievement to accomplish targets. The author maintains that tracking and evaluating development initiatives allows government authorities, development supervisors, and community groups to gain insight from previous experiences, improve how they provide services, plan, and allocate resources, and demonstrate results as a means of transparency to key stakeholders. The author affirms that Statistics South Africa's Service Delivery Improvement Plan (SDIP) focuses on offering an ongoing approach to improvement on essential goods that are in keeping with the Batho Pele principles, which help to guarantee timely and effective service delivery by putting "people first."

As per the article 'Journal of Business Research' by Romero (2020), Nigeria has been active in engaging stakeholders in decision-making that affects service delivery to its people. According to the author, similar initiatives in Nigeria have helped to establish trust among citizens and stakeholders. Engaging them demonstrates that you recognize and respect their thoughts and interests. Therefore, you gain their confidence and credibility. When stakeholders trust in you, they become more supportive and eager to engage, which may lead to new possibilities and beneficial relationships. The author also claims that when stakeholders from various backgrounds collaborate, the opportunity for creativity and innovative problem solutions grows dramatically. Stakeholder talks can generate ideas that would not have occurred within a closed circle of decision-makers. This collaborative approach promotes innovation and results in more effective public service delivery.

According to Waikenda (2020) in his article 'Influence of Stakeholders' Participation on Performance of County Governments in Kenya' Kenya has been actively involving stakeholders in many of its institutional decisions which has seen an improvement in service delivery within the public sector. According to the author, stakeholder analysis, which is

employed in Kenya, is the process of identifying and analyzing the individuals or groups that might or will be affected by your service delivery initiative. It allows you to better grasp their requirements, passions, demands, and potential worries. He also believes that involving stakeholders is critical for effective strategy planning. It entails finding, comprehending, and incorporating those who have an interest in a project involving service delivery to the citizens. Effective stakeholder engagement management necessitates a complete strategy that involves continual interaction, attentiveness, and cooperation in the entire procedure.

Some of the key aspects of stakeholder engagement clarity are; stakeholder engagements should be well-documented, complete with step-by-step guides, flowcharts, and any relevant information that can support understanding, and having standardized processes creates consistency, making it easier for team members to follow established protocols and reduce variability in outcomes. It also involves an open channel of communication are essential for clarifying any ambiguities about engagements (Yang 2023). Regular discussions and updates can help reinforce understanding. Providing training sessions for employees can help them gain a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder engagements, which promotes clarity and adherence and encouraging feedback from team members can help identify areas of confusion or inefficiency in engagements, which can then be addressed to enhance clarity (Zaheer et al., 2024).

Employees who believe that the outcome is the product of their actions and have good relationships with their leaders are seen to have a considerably greater level of role clarity, which has a substantial influence on work performance and commitment than those who lack all of these aspects (Hegazy et al., 2023; Kauppila, 2014). When an organization hires people who are overqualified and have an empowering attitude, job clarity increases significantly, which has a considerable impact on work outcomes or work performance but when work autonomy exceeds networking abilities, it has a greater influence on in-role performance (Ma et al., 2020; Nesheim, Olsen, Sandvik, 2017). If employees are free to perform their tasks transparent with internal communication, collaboration, and flexible work arrangements then they feel at ease at work which enhances work performance, well-being, and motivation but developing networking skills and work autonomy corresponds with positive in-role and extra-role performance (Fincke et al., 2020; Nesheim, Olsen, Sandvik, 2017).

Muthini (2017) researched on stakeholder engagement clarity and performance in the context of Kenya Revenue Authority. The research design was a case study. The target population consisted of top management. Data collection was based on both primary and secondary sources. An interview guide was used to collect data from the respondents. The study established that Kenya Revenue Authority has aligned its internal and external strategies and this has resulted in increased total revenue collection.

Sadiq (2020) investigated resource allocation strategy on water services board performance in Kenya. The study adopted both descriptive and correlational designs. The target population of this study was employees of water services board in Kenya. The researcher used stratified random sampling technique to select a sample size of 150 employees from the population of the employees of water services boards. Primary data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires. The questionnaires were administered by the help of research assistants in each and every department. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used. The study findings indicated that the pressure to provide water to the rapidly growing population in Kenya has made it mandatory for the water services boards to come up with clear cut strategies to meet these demands.

Hu and Liden (2015) posit that stakeholder engagement clarity in goals and processes at the employee and team level is positively related to employee and team performance as well as organizational efficiency as a whole. Clear procedures toward goals are also very important for employee and team performance, because stakeholder engagement clarity provides clearer and more active plans and visible strategies to achieve the goal. Therefore, employees must achieve stakeholder engagement clarity in terms of strategic and operational integration to internalize strategic alignment in their jobs and tasks.

Organizational performance is a set of overall preferred results that it wants to accomplish and measure for different levels of hierarchy and can be assessed for individuals, groups, and the entire organization as a whole (Knies et al., 2016). It is a set of overall preferred results that it wants to accomplish and measure for different levels of hierarchy and can be assessed for individuals, groups, and the entire organization as a whole (Knies et al., 2016). Thus, performance is success that doesn't exist by itself, but it is a function of individual efforts and the result of action (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021).

Non-financial factors that contribute to success include service delivery, quality, dependability, customer satisfaction, and product or service quality (Karanja, 2017). An organization's performance can be clearly shown using a combination of

monetary and nonmonetary metrics. The effectiveness of a company's performance in achieving its objectives can be determined (Cascio, 2006). Performance will be measured by operational efficiency, cost reduction and market share. Despite the many studies that have been conducted globally and locally on strategic alignment and performance, these studies do not show the implications of strategic alignment and performance in the context of County government of Kisii. For instance, the results of a study conducted by Ahmadi, Salamzadeh, Daraei, and Akbari (2017) in Iran cannot be generalized to County government, as a result of differences in economic, political and operational environment.

In addition, Muthini (2017) researched on strategic alignment and performance in the context of County government. This study found out that the alignment of both internal and external strategies has resulted in the success of the firm. Sabherwal, Sabherwal, and Havakhor (2019) investigated how strategic alignment affect firm performance. Although the study focuses majorly on ICT, this will not produce contingent results to generalize to County government as it was narrow in scope since only IT alignment was used.

3. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design. This study was conducted in County government of Kisii. Thus, the target population for the study was 72 comprising of all middle level management in County government of Kisii, Kenya. Since the study population was small, the study worked with entire population which is census. Data collection instruments were questionnaires and other information relevant to the study. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. After collecting the data, it was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness and consistency. It was coded, entered and analysed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SSPS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA multiple linear regression analysis was adopted and computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The objective of the study was to examine the effect of stakeholder engagement clarity on firm performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on various statements relating to the effect of stakeholder engagement clarity on firm performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 4.1.

From the results, the respondents agreed that the corporation documents tasks procedures through user manuals. This is supported by a mean of 3.615 (std. dv = 0.797). In addition, as shown by a mean of 4.696 (std. dv = 0.709), the respondents agreed that the employees are supported to understand the expectations and outcomes of their roles. Further, the respondents agreed that the organization has procedure charts for all major stakeholder engagement. This is shown by a mean of 3.592 (std. dv = 0.691). The respondents also agreed that the stakeholder are oriented on new processes before rolling out. This is shown by a mean of 4.526 (std. dv = 0.695). With a mean of 4.405 (std. dv = 0.773), the respondents agreed that the decisions made by the organization should be communicated to all stakeholders. Lastly, the respondents agreed that strategic stakeholder's engagement enhances organizational performance. This is shown by a mean of 4.241 (std. dv = 0.644).

Table 4.1: Stakeholder Engagement Clarity on the Performance of County Government of Kisii in Kenya

	Mean	Std. Deviation
The corporation documents tasks procedures through user manuals	3.615	0.797
The employees are supported to understand the expectations and outcomes of their roles	4.696	0.709
The organization has procedure charts for all major stakeholder engagement	3.592	0.691
The stakeholder are oriented on new processes before rolling out	4.526	0.695
The decisions made by the organization should be communicated to all stakeholders	4.405	0.773
Strategic stakeholder's engagement enhances organizational performance	4.241	0.644
Aggregate	4.179	0.718

4.1. Effect of Performance of County Government of Kisii in Kenya.

The objective was to assess the effect of on performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya. The reliability for performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement

on various statements relating to the effect of on performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya. The reliability for performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in table 4.2.

From the results, the respondents agreed that the success of any organisation is measured by its ability to achieve set goals and objectives. This is supported by a mean of 4.261 (std. dv = 0.957). In addition, as shown by a mean of 3.958 (std. dv = 0.802), the respondents agreed that performance of the county government is attained when an organization efficiently and effectively achieves its objectives, surpassing its competitors in the process. The respondents further agreed that customer satisfaction, should be exercised in the organization. This is shown by a mean of 3.803 (std. dv = 0.752). The respondents also agreed that the organization should minimize its costs for proper management. This is shown by a mean of 3.792 (std. dv = 0.843). With a mean of 3.743 (std. dv = 0.925), the respondents agreed that strategic management clarity enhances performance. The respondent also agreed that The organization should have clear and precise goals, vision as well as stakeholders engagement and on communication. This is shown by a mean of 3.761 (std. dv = 0.901).

Table 4.2: Performance of County Government of Kisii in Kenya.

	Mean	Std. Deviation
The success of any organization is measured by its ability to achieve set goals and objectives	4.261	0.957
Performance of the county government is attained when an organization efficiently and effectively achieves its objectives, surpassing its competitors in the process	3.958	0.802
Customer satisfaction, should be exercised in the organization	3.803	0.752
The organization should minimize its costs for proper management	3.792	0.843
Strategic management clarity enhances performance.	3.543	0.925
The organization should have clear and precise goals, vision as well as stakeholders engagement and on communication	3.761	0.901
Aggregate	3.853	0.863

4.2 Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics in the current study focused on correlation and regression analysis. Correlation analysis was used to determine the strength of the relationship while regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between dependent variable (performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya) and the independent variable (stakeholder engagement clarity).

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

The present study used Pearson correlation analysis to determine the strength of association between independent variables (stakeholder engagement clarity) and the dependent variable (performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya) dependent variable. Pearson correlation coefficient range between zero and one, where by the strength of association increase with increase in the value of the correlation coefficients. The current study employed Taylor (2018) correlation coefficient ratings where by 0.80 to 1.00 depicts a very strong relationship, 0.60 to 0.79 depicts strong, 0.40 to 0.59 depicts moderate, 0.20 to 0.39 depicts weak.

Table 4.3: Correlation Coefficients

		Performance of County government of Kisii	Strategic stakeholder clarity
Performance of County government of Kisii	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	60	
Strategic stakeholder clarity	Pearson Correlation	.872**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60

From the results, there was a very strong relationship between strategic stakeholder clarity and performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya ($r = 0.872$, p value = 0.000). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.000 was less than 0.05 (significant level).

4.2.2 Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between independent variables (stakeholder engagement clarity) and the dependent variable (performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya).

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.921	.766	.733	2.128

a. Predictors: (Constant), stakeholder engagement clarity.

The model summary was used to explain the variation in the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The r -squared for the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable was 0.766. This implied that 76.6% of the variation in the dependent variable (performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya) could be explained by independent variables (stakeholder engagement clarity).

Table 4.5: Analysis of Variance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	111.326	1	37.311	54.927	.001 ^b
1 Residual	10.237	59	.070		
Total	121.553	60			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya

b. Predictors: (Constant), stakeholder engagement clarity

The ANOVA was used to determine whether the model was a good fit for the data. F calculated was 54.927 while the F critical was 2.044. The p value was 0.000. Since the F -calculated was greater than the F -critical and the p value 0.000 was less than 0.05, the model was considered as a good fit for the data. Therefore, the model can be used to predict the influence of stakeholder engagement clarity on performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya.

Table 4.6: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.675	.108		5.582	.000
	Strategic Stakeholder Clarity	.782	.227	3.275	3.381	.000

a Dependent Variable: Performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya

Table 4.6 showed that if stakeholder engagement clarity is held constant, performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya would be at 0.675.

Performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya = 0.675 + 0.782 (stakeholder engagement clarity).

The regression model was as follows:

$$Y = 0.675 + 0.782X_3 + \varepsilon$$

According to the results, strategic stakeholder engagement clarity has significant effect on performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya ($\beta_1 = 0.782$, p value = 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.002 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The specific objective of the study was to examine the effect of stakeholder engagement clarity on the performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya. The finding that the corporation documents tasks procedures through user manuals and employees are supported to understand the expectations and outcomes of their roles. Further, the findings also indicated that the organization has procedure charts for all major stakeholder engagement and that the stakeholder are oriented on new processes before rolling out. The findings further revealed that the decisions made by the organization should be communicated to all stakeholders and that strategic stakeholder's engagement enhances organizational performance. In conclusion, the results revealed that strategic stakeholder engagement clarity has significant effect on performance of County government of Kisii in Kenya ($\beta_1=0.782$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.002 was less than the significant level of 0.05. The study came up with the following recommendations; the county government should have procedural charts for all major stakeholder engagement and orient them on new processes before rolling out.

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